

Abstract

New Perspective on Acupuncture in Microsystems.

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Acupuncture microsystems represent a diverse yet coherent group of therapeutic approaches that share fundamental clinical and theoretical perspectives. Systems such as auriculotherapy, scalp acupuncture, and *Sujok*, alongside other reflex-based models, exhibit significant parallels both among themselves and with distal systemic approaches, including Tung's acupuncture and Richard Tan's Balance Method. These similarities are particularly evident in the prioritisation of distal treatment strategies, the capacity to induce rapid analgesic effects, the application of a minimal number of needles, and a reduced requirement for intense needle stimulation.

Microsystems are centred on the holographic representation of the body, wherein specific zones or regions reflect the whole, allowing localised stimulation to achieve systemic therapeutic effects. This perspective is intrinsically linked to channel balance theory, which emphasises the restoration of functional equilibrium between meridians rather than focusing solely on local pathology. In clinical practice across these systems, the identification of reactive points and zones is prioritised over pre-defined locations based on fixed *cun* measurements. Consequently, these reactive areas serve as both therapeutic targets and diagnostic indicators—external manifestations of internal dysfunction.

Emerging research into fascial tensegrity provides a contemporary biomechanical model that may elucidate the immediate and distal effects commonly observed in microsystem acupuncture. By viewing the body as a continuous, interconnected web of tension and compression, the transmission of a stimulus from a distal microsystem point to a target organ or region becomes biologically plausible.

Taken together, these convergent principles support a structured and reproducible approach to acupuncture that complements traditional Chinese medicine (TCM). This integrated model may reduce methodological heterogeneity in research by facilitating the development of protocols based on shared mechanisms and defined clinical phenomena. Such standardisation will enable the creation of comparable studies, strengthening the evidence base and advancing the standing of acupuncture within the hierarchy of scientific evidence.

Keywords: Acupuncture; Acupuncture Analgesia; Distal Acupuncture.

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